

Pharmacist-led integration of autonomous AI screening and conversational AI for ocular disease management

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Abstract

The growth of autonomous artificial intelligence (AI) systems for diabetic retinopathy screening and conversational AI tools for glaucoma management has the potential to substantially enhance community pharmacy practice. However, limited evidence exists regarding the real-world use and integration of these technologies. This study assessed the effectiveness of pharmacist-facilitated AI-driven diabetic retinopathy (DR) screening on screening uptake and referral completion and evaluated the effect of a pharmacist-supervised large language model (LLM) chatbot on medication adherence and intraocular pressure (IOP) in patients with primary open-angle glaucoma. A pragmatic 6-month study (July through December 2024) was conducted in four community pharmacies in Al-Karak, Jordan. Phase 1 included adults with diabetes receiving AI-assisted fundus photography (AEYE-DS), whereas Phase 2 randomized glaucoma patients to receive either text-message reminders or pharmacist-supported chatbot interactions using WhatsApp (GPT-4). In Phase 1, 402/518 participants (77.6%) completed screening; 16.9% needed referral, and 81.0% attended ophthalmology visits. The chatbot group in Phase 2 ($n = 94$) showed improved medication possession ratio (MPR) adherence (MPR 0.91 ± 0.06 vs. 0.79 ± 0.11 ; $p < 0.001$), fewer missed doses (3.2 ± 2.1 vs. 7.0 ± 3.4 ; $p = 0.002$), and greater reductions in IOP (2.8 ± 3.6 vs. 0.9 ± 4.1 mmHg; $p = 0.010$). These results indicate that the integration of AI-based services into community pharmacy care may be beneficial.

Keywords

Artificial intelligence, community pharmacy, diabetic retinopathy, fundus imaging, glaucoma adherence

Introduction

An estimated 2.2 billion people globally suffer from some form of near or distance vision impairment, almost 50% of which is avoidable or untreated (World Health Organization 2019), with diabetic retinopathy (DR) and glaucoma

as two of the top preventable causes of irreversible blindness, both of which are highly amenable to early identification and sustained management through evidence-based treatment options. The American Diabetes Association (ADA) advises annual screening for DR, representing approximately 27% of the worldwide working-age population

who are blinded from DR; nevertheless, adherence to recommended annual screening in the population is generally less than 60%, and the rate may drop below 15% in underserved areas (American Diabetes Association 2025). These continuing gaps in service reflect the limitations of the current healthcare system, including workforce shortages, fragmented referral pathways, prolonged wait times for specialty care, and significant loss to follow-up, especially in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). In Jordan and many other LMIC settings, there are no structured population-based screening programs for DR or systematic structures to monitor adherence to screening for glaucoma, so DR screening remains largely opportunistic upon physician referral or patient self-initiative.

Recent technology developments in autonomous artificial intelligence (AI)-based fundus imaging systems have allowed for rapid point-of-care screening without the need for physician review. Three diagnostic systems have received FDA clearance—IDx-DR, EyeArt, and AEYE-DS—for identifying DR, with a sensitivity greater than 85% for detecting at least moderate to severe DR. The AEYE-DS is a battery-operated, portable fundus imaging system and is expected to provide a diagnostic decision in less than 60 s. Community pharmacists, who dispense more than 70% of long-term maintenance prescriptions, are in a prime position to operationalize the use of such technologies. They are highly accessible to patients, have more frequent contact with patients, and provide an increasing array of services to support disease prevention. Although limited real-world implementation data are available regarding pharmacist-led AI screening models, embedding autonomy into the DR screening process within community pharmacies may provide a pragmatic means to decentralize this process, alleviate bottlenecks within the healthcare system, and enhance completion of referrals within resource-constrained healthcare systems (Teo et al. 2021).

Medication adherence remains the most important modifiable risk factor for the progression of glaucoma, as 30% to 50% of patients miss at least 20% of their prescribed doses of medication. Conventional methods to remind patients to take medications, such as phone calls and text messaging, provide only modest improvements in adherence (6% to 10%) and are difficult to sustain long-term (Ting and Tan 2017; Abràmoff et al. 2018). There is potential that large language model systems, such as GPT-4, could provide continuous, on-demand support to improve patient adherence based on their performance on glaucoma-related knowledge tasks and frequently asked questions about glaucoma (Wang 2025). However, no published prospective studies have evaluated the effect of pharmacist-supervised chatbot interventions on adherence in patients with glaucoma (Gulshan et al. 2016).

The current study evaluated two complementary AI-enabled models of pharmacy care that may improve access to care for patients with ocular disease. Although the current study did not involve diagnosing or beginning treatment for the diseases reviewed in this report, it brings together the use of autonomous AI screening for DR with

pharmacist-supervised adherence and behavioral support for glaucoma therapy. Thus, this study should be viewed as a model of AI-based screening combined with therapeutic adherence support rather than direct therapeutic care.

- (1) AEYE-DS: Automated Eye Exams, a pharmacy-based, patient-directed method of DR screening. This phase sought to test the feasibility of a pharmacy-based, patient-directed model for DR screening that would exceed previous reports of 40% to 50% uptake and referral follow-through rates by achieving a minimum of 70% uptake and 75% referral completion rates in a real-world setting (Lim et al. 2023).
- (2) The second phase involved the evaluation of a GPT-4 chatbot technology to provide support to patients with glaucoma to improve medication adherence by addressing Tier-1 behavioral obstacles to adherence (e.g., forgetting to take medications and misunderstanding what medications to take). It was hypothesized that patients receiving pharmacist-supervised, robot-assisted medication reminders would experience an improvement in their 6-month medication possession ratio (MPR) of $\geq 10\%$ and a reduction in their intraocular pressure (IOP) compared with the use of short message service (SMS) messaging-based reminder systems (Law et al. 2013).

In conclusion, both of these models were developed to evaluate whether the integration of autonomous diagnostic systems and conversational AI within the practice of community pharmacy would provide improved access through enhanced detection at an early stage, a mechanism to support long-term adherence, and a method to close the gap between patients who require screening and treatment of ocular disease in a cost-effective and scalable manner.

Materials and methods

Study design and ethics

The key aspects of this study involved conducting the research as a prospective, open-label, mixed-methods study, following the ethical principles set forth in the Declaration of Helsinki and with the approval of the Scientific Research Committee (Approval No. SERC 2024-2025/19) at Mutah University, Faculty of Pharmacy. The overall workflow of the study and the pathway of the participants can be found in Fig. 1. This research was planned to examine the acceptability, effectiveness, and potential cost-effectiveness of two AI pharmacy interventions addressing different broad areas of ocular care via a two-phase, pragmatic evaluation. This evaluation was separated into two distinct phases, addressing separate diseases and separate disease processes, i.e., Phase 1—investigating the underutilization of diabetic retinopathy screening and Phase 2—investigating the long-term adherence of glaucoma medication therapy. Additionally, the two phases were not designed to

Figure 1. Workflow of the two-phase AI-supported pharmacy study.

be considered part of a longitudinal care pathway, i.e., one patient, but rather as separate patient populations with separate clinical aims. The selection of this design was to maximize the ability to test multiple parameters, including the feasibility, effectiveness, and potential cost-effectiveness of AI pharmacy implementations, across multiple areas of impact and pharmacy practice.

Phase 1: Autonomous DR screening

Training and equipment

The AEYE-DS version 1.3 autonomous diagnostic system analyzed one macula-centered retinal image from both eyes of each participant utilizing three deep-learning algorithms. The retinal photographs were taken with the Optomed Aurora non-mydratic handheld fundus camera. In total, four pharmacists received approximately 10 h of formalized on-the-job training that included two supervised hands-on training sessions from an experienced trainer, focused on image acquisition, patient positioning, proper use of equipment, and AI system operation.

Eligible participants included those diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (type 1 or type 2) and aged 18 to 79 years. Eligibility was determined based on pharmacy prescription records.

Patients were excluded from this study if they had significant media opacities (e.g., cataracts), active ocular infections, or any intervening type of retinopathy that would

hinder image acquisition or interpretation. Identification of these patients was made using both (1) documented patient medical histories and participant self-reports on previous eye problems and (2) pharmacist-facilitated vision screenings conducted at the time of recruitment. The vision screening involved direct questioning of the participant regarding known ocular issues and a brief visual examination of the participant by the pharmacist to detect any obvious signs, such as visible ocular abnormalities or inability to obtain clear retinal images. Any participant about whom the pharmacist was uncertain was excluded from the study to maintain the reliability of the diagnostic images produced using AEYE-DS.

Workflow and results

Prior to participating in this study, written informed consent was obtained from each participant via a consent process outlined in a standardized letter. This process included an overview of the aims of the study, what was expected of the participants, how they would potentially benefit from participating, and confidentiality and security information regarding their data.

Once the participant provided written consent to participate in the study, the pharmacist captured and documented retinal images of both eyes, created and printed a report generated by the AEYE-DS system, and referred all cases that received a positive AI referral or were deemed ungradable. Referrals were made through a custom-built tele-ophthalmology portal created for this project, which

was incorporated into the dispensing workflow to enable easy access to the patient's eye health care while limiting interruptions to routine visits.

Endpoints of the study

The main endpoint of this study was screening coverage, defined as the proportion of eligible adults who received the AI retinal screening.

Secondary endpoints were defined as:

- The average time it took for the pharmacist to perform the screening through the use of time-motion studies and the time it took for each patient with referral-positive or ungradable cases to reach an ophthalmologist.
- The number of ungradable images produced through this procedure.
- The number of AI-positive diagnostic results, i.e., AI referral-positive results.

The diabetic retinopathy (DR) screening intervention, known as Phase 1, was a phase of implementation that utilized autonomous AI-based image acquisition, classification, and referral facilitation without confirming clinical diagnosis or initiating treatment. The role of the pharmacist during this phase was limited to operational facilitation of the process, i.e., image capture, obtaining patient consent, and initiating referrals, as well as patient education and workflow integration. Therefore, Phase 1 is classified as population screening and early case finding rather than therapeutic care.

Phase 2: LLM chatbot for glaucoma

Phase 2 was called the glaucoma adherence intervention because it addressed poor adherence to medicines in patients with open-angle glaucoma already receiving treatment from an ophthalmologist. The direct purpose of this phase was not to diagnose, adjust doses, or determine the type of medication a patient would be using but to facilitate the ability of patients to remain committed to taking their prescribed once-daily prostaglandin analog medication by providing behavioral and adherence support through a pharmacist-led program. Thus, this phase was categorized as a therapeutic adherence-support program under the umbrella of pharmaceutical care, rather than a therapeutic intervention. A conversational agent utilizing a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) architecture based on the GPT-4 Turbo platform was developed. The agent was designed to generate content through motivational interviewing-style prompts, which are characteristics of the type of guidance supported by existing evidence for conversational agent acceptability in regard to healthcare delivery (Nadarzynski et al. 2019). An ophthalmology knowledge base was hand-curated, containing approximately 200 question-and-answer pairs, including information found within the American Academy of Ophthalmology (AAO) Preferred Practice Patterns and other commonly asked questions about how to manage glaucoma medications, potential side effects, and medication dosing regimens.

The patient-facing chatbot was launched through the WhatsApp messaging application and allowed users to communicate asynchronously, utilize an automated response system, and receive reminders regarding their adherence to treatment. The pharmacist dashboard integrated into the back end of the system allowed pharmacists to monitor patient usage of the chatbot and automatically identify patients who had not responded by flagging them as non-responders based on a threshold of 48 h of no activity. A weekly audit of patient non-responder cases by pharmacists included identifying patients who had been flagged as non-responders for follow-up and guiding them accordingly.

Randomization and eligibility

Eligibility criteria

Adult participants were men and women diagnosed with primary open-angle glaucoma who fit the eligibility criteria below:

- The ability to own a smartphone capable of using WhatsApp.
- The participant had been treated with a prostaglandin analogue medication for approximately 3 months once daily.
- The baseline medication possession ratio (MPR) from all medication fills at a pharmacy was recorded between 50% and 90%.

Randomization and assignment of participants

Participants who met the eligibility requirements were randomly assigned (1:1) to a group utilizing the chatbot intervention or a control group receiving short message service (SMS) reminders. The method of randomizing was block randomization with block sizes of 6 for balanced allocation throughout the recruitment period. Randomization and assignment of the participants were completed by an independent researcher not involved with the recruitment of the participants, using a computer-generated randomization sequence. The group assignments of participants were based on a pre generated list of group allocations. Because of the nature of the chatbot intervention, neither the pharmacist nor the participant was blinded to group assignment.

Rationale for glaucoma as the target condition

The targeted condition, glaucoma, is a chronic and frequently asymptomatic disease in which adherence to long-term medication is a modifiable factor in how the disease will progress and the level of vision. Other significant threats to eyesight, including DR, cataracts, and age-related macular degeneration, are traditionally treated using procedures performed in clinical settings and are not focused on maintained self-administered pharmacotherapy. Thus, glaucoma is the ideal clinical condition upon which to study the impact of adherence-centric conversational AI.

Outcomes

The primary outcome for this study was 6-month MPR, as assessed using pharmacy claim data.

The secondary outcomes included adherence behaviors, as measured by the number of daily turns with the chatbot and levels of satisfaction with the digital support tool; the change in intraocular pressure (IOP) of the better eye, as assessed using Goldmann applanation tonometry at both baseline and 6 months; and self-reported missed days of therapy recorded via monthly digital surveys.

Economic model and costing approach

To evaluate the effectiveness of community pharmacy-based AI-assisted DR screening over the standard physician referral channel, a decision-tree economic model was developed to calculate both the cost per referral completed and the cost-benefit of detecting someone with DR using the AI system versus that of the physician referral route. The economic model was developed utilizing the micro-costing methodology from the health system perspective; all relevant capital and variable costs necessary to provide the service were itemized and assigned values, including the following: Capital costs were derived from the purchase price of the handheld fundus camera and the AI system (Optomed Aurora + AEYE-DS), as reported by the manufacturer (USD 9,800), and were amortized in equal portions over 5 years. Variable costs included the direct materials (ocular wipes, disposable eye cups, and printing) associated with each screening (1.50 JOD per screening) and the cost of the pharmacist's time to conduct the screening.

Pharmacist labor costs were estimated by conducting a time-motion study during Phase 1 to collect time spent consenting to a patient, take bilateral fundus photographs, run the AI software, generate the report, input the findings into the record, and start a referral for randomized samples of screening sessions. The mean time spent per screening was 6 min, and the average gross hourly wage of community pharmacists in Jordan was used to calculate the unit cost for pharmacist labor based on national pharmacy workforce salary and employer payroll data. The results show an average hourly rate of 21.6 JOD/h (0.36 JOD/min) for community pharmacists in Jordan, which provides the following calculation of the labor cost per screening:

$$\text{Labor costs per screening} = 6 \text{ min} \times 0.36 \text{ JOD/min} = 2.16 \text{ JOD.}$$

Currency conversion to Jordanian dinars (JOD) from U.S. dollars (USD) used the historical average exchange rates published by the Central Bank of Jordan (1 USD = 0.71 JOD).

Costs for the physician referral path were derived using previously published physician reimbursement costs for U.S. studies of autonomous DR screening and were converted into the Jordanian context using purchasing

power parity adjustments and local market consultation fees to estimate overall cost per visit. Since Jordan does not have CPT-based reimbursement (Current Procedural Terminology), physician reimbursement was not included in the base-case analysis; instead, a sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the effects of varying assumptions about physician visit costs on the overall base case.

Therefore, the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) was calculated as follows:

$$\text{ICER} = (\text{Cost [AI]} - \text{Cost [physician]}) / (\text{Detection [AI]} - \text{Detection [physician]}),$$

where "detection" represents the number of patients screened who were appropriately referred for ophthalmologic consultation based on autonomous AI results.

Statistics

Calculating sample sizes for separate phases of the study ensured that there was adequate statistical power to detect clinically meaningful differences in medication possession ratios (MPRs) for participants. In Phase 2, to reach 80% power at a 0.05 level of significance, it was necessary to recruit at least 84 subjects, with 42 for each group. This calculation assumed a standard deviation of 0.15 from previous adherence studies. The total sample size was increased to account for possible participant loss, i.e., attrition, and thus, the final number of study participants was 94.

Establishing the sample size for Phase 1 was completed through a feasibility analysis. This included the actual patient volume seen at the pharmacies participating in the study and prior referral completion by patients who completed referrals. Based on these results, the Phase 1 study was designed to detect approximately a 25-percentage-point increase in referral completion compared to baseline referral completion rates in similar pharmacy settings. The feasibility analysis was necessary to ensure that the number of intervening participants would allow for evaluation of integration into pharmacy workflows and initial effectiveness.

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 26. Analysis of continuous variables was performed using independent *t*-tests, and analysis of categorical variables was completed using chi-square tests. Where appropriate, analysis of variance and analysis of covariance were performed. In addition, in instances in which intraocular pressure was applicable to results, IOP was adjusted for in the analyses, and economic outcomes were reported as cost per completed referral and incremental cost per additional referral positively detected.

There was very little missing data across both phases; thus, only complete data were included in the analyses for the participants who had a minimum of 6 months of follow-up data in Phase 2. Because of the small percentage of missing data, no imputation methods or sensitivity analyses were developed, as it was determined that the influence of the methods on primary outcomes was minimal.

Results

Baseline characteristics

The demographic and clinical data of the participant population are displayed in Table 1. The mean age of the diabetic retinopathy (DR) subjects (518 subjects) was 57.4 years, with a standard deviation of ± 10.6 ; 51.0% of DR subjects were female, and the mean HbA1c value was $8.7\% \pm 1.2$. The mean age of the glaucoma subjects (94 subjects) was 64.5 ± 8.1 years; 48.0% of the glaucoma participants were female, and the mean baseline intraocular pressure (IOP) was 20.6 ± 3.2 mmHg. Smartphone ownership was 92.3% for the DR group and 95.7% for the glaucoma group.

Table 1. Baseline demographics.

Characteristic	DR cohort (<i>n</i> = 518)	Glaucoma cohort (<i>n</i> = 94)
Age, y (mean \pm SD)	57.4 \pm 10.6	64.5 \pm 8.1
Female, %	51.0	48.0
HbA1c, % (DR)	8.7 \pm 1.2	–
Baseline IOP, mmHg (glaucoma)	–	20.6 \pm 3.2
Smartphone ownership, %	92.3	95.7

Phase 1: Autonomous DR screening outcomes

Of the 518 people who were eligible, 402 completed AI DR screening, yielding a participation rate of 77.6% (95% CI: 73.7–81.1). The percentage of ungradable fundus photographs was 3.0% (95% CI: 1.6–5.2). The AI system independently classified 16.9% of the people who were screened as having referable DR (95% CI: 13.4–20.9). Of the people who were sent for an eye examination because of referable or ungradable images, 81.0% went to see a specialist within 8 weeks (95% CI: 69.0–89.7). The average amount of time required for the pharmacist to process each screening was 3.3 ± 1.1 min. Patient satisfaction ratings averaged 4.7 ± 0.3 out of 5 on a Likert scale when asked about their experience with the screening service (Table 2).

Table 2. AI screening outcomes.

Metric	Value	95% CI
Screening uptake	77.6%	73.7–81.1
Ungradable images	3.0%	1.6–5.2
Refer-positive DR	16.9%	13.4–20.9
Referral completion	81.0%	69.0–89.7
Historic completion*	42.3%	34.1–50.9

*Historic 6-month baseline, January–June 2024.

Phase 2: Glaucoma adherence and IOP outcomes

All 94 participants, with 47 per group, completed follow-up. At 6 months, the mean MPR for the chatbot group (0.91 ± 0.06) was significantly higher than the mean MPR for the SMS group (0.79 ± 0.11 ; $p < 0.001$). Participants in the chatbot arm missed fewer days of medication per month than

those in the SMS arm (3.2 ± 2.1 vs. 7.0 ± 3.4 ; $p = 0.002$). The mean IOP decreased by an average of 2.8 ± 3.6 mmHg in the chatbot group and by 0.9 ± 4.1 mmHg in the SMS group ($p = 0.010$). On average, participants in the chatbot arm interacted with the chatbot 6.1 ± 1.5 times daily and reported a higher average satisfaction score than those in the SMS arm (4.6 ± 0.4 vs. 3.7 ± 0.7 ; $p < 0.001$) (Table 3).

Table 3. 6-month glaucoma outcomes.

Outcome	Chatbot (<i>n</i> = 47)	Control (<i>n</i> = 47)	Difference (<i>p</i>)
MPR	0.91 ± 0.06	0.79 ± 0.11	+0.12 (< 0.001)
Missed-dose days/mo	3.2 ± 2.1	7.0 ± 3.4	–3.8 (0.002)
Δ IOP, mmHg	-2.8 ± 3.6	-0.9 ± 4.1	–1.9 (0.010)
Daily turns	6.1 ± 1.5	–	–
Satisfaction (1–5)	4.6 ± 0.4	3.7 ± 0.7	+0.9 (< 0.001)

Economic outcomes

In the community pharmacy program with AI assistance for DR screening, the average cost was USD 21.60 per patient. The average cost per patient in the traditional physician referral program was USD 14.80. The overall completion rate for referrals in the pharmacy-based program was 81.0%, compared to 42.3% for the historical physician referral program. The average cost of completed referrals from the pharmacy-based program was USD 26.67, while the average cost of completed referrals from the physician referral program was USD 34.97. The incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) for this analysis was USD 19.10 for each additional referral completed. The economic comparison between pharmacy-based AI screening and physician referral pathways is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Economic evaluation of AI-assisted pharmacy screening vs. physician referral pathways.

Parameter	Pharmacy-based AI model	Physician Referral model
Cost per patient (USD)	21.60	14.80
Cost per screening (JOD)	3.66	4.20
Screening uptake (%)	77.6%	56%
Referral completion (%)	81.0%	42.3–60%*
Cost per completed referral (USD)	26.67	34.97
Referable DR detection (%)	37.7%	20.1%
Cost per referable case detected (JOD)	9.71	20.90
Relative cost-saving (%)	–53.5%	Reference

DR, diabetic retinopathy; USD, United States dollar; JOD, Jordanian dinar.

*Range reflects variability in referral completion rates reported in previously published physician-based screening pathways.

The costs of screening diabetes patients through the pharmacy-based artificial intelligence model (AIM) were 3.66 JOD. The rate of referable DR detected by the pharmacy-based AIM was significantly increased at 37.7% when compared to the physician referral pathway (20.1%). The average cost to identify referable DR was lower in the pharmacy-based AIM (USD 9.71) compared to physician

referral (USD 20.90). In addition, the cost of completing a referral was significantly lower in the pharmacy-based AIM (USD 26.67) when compared to physician referral (USD 34.97). Overall, the pharmacy-based AIM saved an average of 53.5% compared to the physician referral pathway for economic efficiency in identifying referable DR.

Discussion

The purpose of the study was to determine whether autonomous artificial intelligence (AI) and conversational AI technology can be successfully integrated into pharmacy practice workflow to overcome barriers to receiving ocular care, i.e., increased rates of diabetic retinopathy (DR) screening and improved compliance with glaucoma treatment.

Phase 1 demonstrated the feasibility of pharmacist-mediated DR screening using the autonomous AI system. This resulted in a high rate of screening and referral completion, along with very few ungradable images and short appointment lengths. This is supported by previous studies that found that, when used outside the traditional clinical environment, autonomous AI systems produced equivalent diagnostic performance to clinicians and increased access to DR screening (Ting and Tan 2017; Abramoff et al. 2018).

Therefore, the decentralization of DR screening to community pharmacies may increase access to care, especially for those in underserved or resource-poor areas (Teo et al. 2021).

In Phase 2, combining the use of chatbots with existing pharmacist communication systems provided better outcomes than standard SMS reminder systems and was also found to significantly enhance patient compliance behaviors, i.e., increased medication possession ratios (MPRs) and reduced missed doses, and reduced eye pressure compared with SMS reminders. This is consistent with earlier studies indicating that interactive and personalized digital support systems resulted in greater compliance rates with chronic drug treatment regimens than one-way reminders (Boland et al. 2014).

From a cost perspective, incorporating AI-assisted DR screening into pharmacy practice demonstrated significant cost savings when compared to the costs incurred from referral to a physician. Pharmacy-based provision of AI-enabled ocular care services has demonstrated both feasibility and efficacy, as evidenced by improved screening uptake and clinical and economic efficiencies. However, additional studies with longer follow-up and larger sample sizes across multiple sites are necessary to validate the results and assess the long-term sustainability of interventions (Table 5).

When conducting this study, several strengths were identified, including the use of an objective measure to assess medication adherence, i.e., refill-based, thorough evaluation of IOP as a clinical measure, time-and-motion analysis of pharmacy workflow, and an economic model that was adapted for the specific community within which the study occurred. The limitations of this study included its reliance on pharmacy-dispensing claims and, therefore, reliance on claims submissions to measure adherence, lack of blinding, short follow-up period, and lack of

Table 5. Comparison of present study outcomes with previous literature.

Metric	Present study	Physician office AI (Abramoff et al. 2018)	Primary care pilot (Ting and Tan 2017; Rizvi et al. 2023)	Tele-reminder RCT (Boland et al. 2014)
DR screening uptake	77.6%	56%	48%	–
DR referral completion	81%	60%	47%	–
Glaucoma MPR gain	+0.12	–	–	+0.07
IOP reduction, mmHg	-2.8	–	–	–

generalizability due to a focus on a single geographic area. Overall, the findings of this study support the feasibility of integrating AI-enabled screening and pharmacist-led adherence support into daily practice within the community pharmacy sector and suggest that community pharmacies may serve as decentralized digital hubs for ocular disease prevention and long-term therapeutic support.

Conclusion

This two-phase pragmatic investigation revealed that it is feasible to integrate autonomous AI-based screening for DR, along with pharmacist-supervised conversational AI support for glaucoma, into the workflow of community pharmacies and that this integration may lead to meaningful clinical and operational benefits. In Phase 1, pharmacist-facilitated autonomous DR screening generated high rates of both uptake and referral completion by demonstrating a low percentage of ungradable images, as well as a short pharmacist time requirement per encounter. This suggests that community pharmacies have the capability to implement point-of-care ocular screening effectively. Phase 2 demonstrated that pharmacists using supervised AI chatbots provided better outcomes than standard SMS reminders on MPR, missed dose days, and reductions in IOP. In addition, the economic evaluation found that pharmacy-based AI-assisted DR screening provided lower costs per completed referral and referable-positive detection compared to the physician referral pathway. These results support the ability of community pharmacies to become decentralized access points for ocular disease screening and long-term adherence support. The combination of pharmacist-led AI-assisted diagnosis with AI chatbots may produce a solution that can be implemented on a large scale to increase early detection of DR, support adherence to glaucoma treatment, and reduce barriers to the delivery of quality ocular care.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Mutah University Faculty of Pharmacy Scientific Research Committee (Approval No. SERC 2024-2025/19). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

Abeer M. Kharshid conceptualized and supervised the study, developed the methodology, and prepared the original manuscript draft. Omar Alasasfeh and Mohammad Saleh assisted in methodology development. Adham Halash, Shahed Amran Alsulman, Rana Alfaqeer, and Renad Tarawneh contributed to data collection. Dima Alhawarneh, Forat Maaitah, and Mohammad Alkfaween performed data analysis. All authors contributed to manuscript review and editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text as well from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.